

Regionalism and International Diplomacy Challenges: Are We Heading toward World War III or a new Cold War?

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Abstract

Objective: This paper looks into how regionalism is changing and how it affects international diplomacy. It assesses the efficacy of regional and international efforts to uphold global peace and security and tries to ascertain whether the current strains on the planet could spark a third world war or another Cold War. **Method:** Both constructivism and realism are used in the study to comprehend regionalism and international diplomacy. Constructivism concentrates on identities and conventions, whereas realism studies power relationships and national interests. The research combines case studies from the past and present, looks at both successful and unsuccessful diplomatic attempts, and assesses the contributions of different regional blocs and international institutions. **Conclusion:** The article's conclusion is that, in response to globalization, regionalism has dramatically changed from state-centric alliances to multidimensional regional organizations. It emphasizes how crucial proactive and strategic diplomacy is to solving today's problems and averting big conflicts. The flexibility of regional alliances, the success of diplomatic initiatives, and the capacity to handle international dangers will determine the direction of international cooperation in the future. Achieving global peace and tackling complex issues requires effective regionalism and international diplomacy.

Descriptors

Regionalism; International Diplomacy; Cold War and World War III; Security Alliances and Economic Integration; Preventive Diplomacy

INTRODUCTION

Regionalism, as defined by Yankson (2023, p. 333 and 338), involves the strengthening of political, economic, and cultural ties among nations within a given region to achieve shared objectives, such as political stability and economic cooperation. With advancements in international relations, technology, and economic conditions, regional alliances have expanded to address issues of security, environmental sustainability, and cultural exchange. Notable examples include the European Union (EU), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), and Mercosur. The cohesion and adaptability of these blocs will shape the future of regionalism as they navigate

evolving challenges.

Building on Yankson's concept, Vöyrynen (2003, p. 25–28) categorizes regionalism into "old" and "new" phases, highlighting distinct stages in regional integration. While old regionalism was marked by state-centric, security-focused alliances such as the OAU and NATO, new regionalism—emerging in a post-Cold War context—is more dynamic, prioritizing regional identity and coherence. Organizations like the EU and Mercosur exemplify new regionalism, where alliances address political, economic, and cultural dimensions beyond mere military or economic agreements.

As regional alliances adapt to shifting global dynamics, diplomacy becomes essential in advancing national and regional interests, as Wattie (2024) describes. Leaders employ diplomacy using various foreign policy tools—trade, sanctions, military power, and international aid—to influence the actions of other nations. High-level negotiations and everyday diplomatic exchanges, often managed by civil servants, enhance regional ties and navigate the complexities of international relations. These efforts illustrate how regionalism and diplomacy interconnect, as alliances like the EU, ASEAN, and AU leverage diplomacy to promote regional cohesion.

The relevance of effective diplomacy is also underscored by current geopolitical tensions, with Deutsch's (1983) analysis providing a psychological perspective on Cold War dynamics. Deutsch identifies mutual mistrust, relentless competition, and the arms race as sustaining factors for hostilities. Today, multilateral efforts—such as the Iranian nuclear negotiations and discussions on North Korea's nuclear programs—demonstrate a collective resolve to avoid a Cold War redux. The interconnected nature of the global economy further complicates isolationist tendencies, offering hope for diplomacy in mitigating regional conflicts.

In specific regions, like the Indian Ocean, the changing security landscape adds another layer to regional dynamics. Corder (2014) emphasizes the growing strategic importance of this region and the instability that arises from power struggles among major actors, including China, India, and the United States. This shift from state-centric to non-state threats exemplifies Vöyrynen's new regionalism, where security is increasingly intertwined with regional identity and cooperation.

Amid these complex dynamics, security theorists such as Buzan, Weaver, and De Wilde (Vreij, 2010) highlight the value of regional institutions for fostering stability. Organizations like the EU, ASEAN, and AU harness the collective security of their member states, illustrating how regionalism enhances security by promoting collaborative responses to common threats. The potential for conflict, however, persists, balancing on the efficacy of such security frameworks.

This paper uses Constructivism and Realism to analyze regionalism and diplomacy. Realism highlights power dynamics and state interests, suggesting tensions may lead to a new Cold War. Constructivism focuses on ideas and identities, exploring how evolving norms influence regional cooperation and stability in today's global landscape.

HISTORICAL OUTLOOK

Regionalism has played a crucial role in shaping international relations and security, particularly during the Cold War when the bipolar power structure led by the US and the USSR limited the autonomy of regional security frameworks. This period saw regional dynamics often dominated by the influence of these superpowers, creating a semi-global system where local security considerations were subordinate to larger geopolitical agendas. Following the Cold War, however, there was an increase in regional autonomy and the rise of regional powers, as Vöyrynen (2003, p. 28–29) notes, though US hegemony and global power dynamics continued to pose challenges for regionalism, particularly in Africa, the Middle East, and Southeast Asia.

In this Cold War context, alliances like the Warsaw Pact became central to the Soviet strategy to counterbalance NATO, as outlined by the Department of State (2017). Created as a political and military coalition among Eastern European nations under Soviet influence, the Warsaw Pact exemplified Cold War-era regionalism in which the autonomy of member states was limited. The Pact's dissolution after the Soviet Union's collapse in 1991 marked the end of an era where regional alliances were primarily designed for collective defense against Western influence and intervention.

Simultaneously, the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) emerged in 1961 as a coalition of nations seeking to maintain neutrality amid Cold War pressures. NAM, as the Embassy of the Kingdom of Bahrain explains, sought to uphold territorial integrity, human rights, and peaceful dispute resolution outside the frameworks dominated by either the Eastern or Western blocs. By promoting principles such as national sovereignty and non-interference, NAM illustrated an alternative form of regionalism that transcended direct Cold War alignments and emphasized cooperation based on equality and international fairness.

The end of the Cold War reshaped global alliances and shifted the balance of power, transitioning from a bipolar to a unipolar world with the United States as the dominant superpower. This shift enabled the expansion of regional organizations like NATO and the EU, as Deutsch (1983, p. 5 e 28) highlights, welcoming Central and Eastern European nations into these alliances and marking an era of deepening regional integration. Additionally, emerging powers such as China and India gained significant influence on the global stage, challenging traditional Western dominance and necessitating new forms of multilateral and regional diplomacy to address complex issues like climate change and cybersecurity.

Vöyrynen (2003, p. 31 e 42) elaborates on how the EU's expansion into Central and Eastern Europe after the Cold War profoundly transformed Europe's political, economic, and security landscape. The enlargement process fostered greater economic integration and political stability, strengthening the EU's position as a regional power. Yet, challenges arose, including economic disparities, immigration tensions, and the growth of populist movements, which test the EU's cohesion. Despite these challenges, the EU continues to prioritize further integration and enlargement as a way to sustain its regional influence and stability.

Similarly, ASEAN's development since its founding in 1967 has exemplified the evolution of regionalism in Southeast Asia. NTI (2022) notes that ASEAN initially sought to foster stability and cooperation in the region through principles such as mutual respect for sovereignty and peaceful conflict resolution. The Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC) in 1976 solidified ASEAN's commitment to regional peace, setting a foundation for cooperation that would eventually include broader goals such as economic growth and social development. This approach has allowed ASEAN to adapt to changing global dynamics while maintaining regional cohesion.

Together, these examples illustrate how regionalism, from the Cold War to the present, has adapted to changing geopolitical realities. Alliances such as the Warsaw Pact and NATO, non-aligned frameworks like NAM, and the development of organizations like the EU and ASEAN each reflect unique aspects of regional cooperation and security. The continuing evolution of these organizations shows how regionalism is influenced by shifts in global power, economic integration, and the need for cooperative approaches to address contemporary challenges in security, climate, and development.

PRESENT-DAY GLOBAL LANDSCAPE

Countries with common goals, such economic integration, collective security, or shared values, create regional blocs and alliances. Two notable instances are NATO, which is devoted to collective defense, and the European Union (EU), which concentrates on political and economic integration in Europe. While the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) place more emphasis on economic and security cooperation in Eurasia and Central Asia, ASEAN fosters regional cooperation in Southeast Asia. The Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP) promotes political and cultural relations among Portuguese-speaking countries, while China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) invests in global infrastructure. Mercosur seeks economic union throughout South America; the G77 assists developing nations in the UN; OPEC coordinates energy policies; and the G20 deals with international political and economic concerns. Baba and Erşen (2023).

According to Yoshimatsu (2022), current regional blocs and alliances influence international politics, economy, and security through promoting international collaboration. Important economic blocs include the USMCA, a trilateral trade deal between the US, Canada, and Mexico; the EU, which unites 27 European countries; and ASEAN, which fosters growth in Southeast Asia. Mercosur promotes trade in South America, whereas the African Union seeks unification among its 55 member states. In terms of politics and security, the Quad strengthens Indo-Pacific security, the SCO and CSTO concentrate on regional stability, NATO guarantees member safety, and BRICS—Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—aims to increase its economic might. These blocs are dynamic, changing in response to obstacles and changes in the world.

As noted by Chisholm and Chissale (2024, pp. 2 and 13), there are multiple important ways in which BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) are challenging Western supremacy. Due to their substantial resources and populations, they possess considerable economic power

on a worldwide scale, altering the dynamics of global trade. The New Development Bank serves as an alternative to Western financial organizations such as the World Bank and the IMF. BRICS reforms aim to represent a more equitable distribution of power in global governance. They also challenge Western cultural and technological dominance by expanding their influence through technological developments and cultural exchanges. BRICS attracts countries seeking varied relationships by broadening trade networks, encouraging South-South collaboration, and providing development funds with fewer limitations. Despite internal divisions, the combined efforts of BRICS indicate a move towards a multipolar world.

Gelot and Söderbaum (2024, p. 821 and 833) note that the African Union (AU), which was founded in 2002 and currently has 55 member states, is essential to advancing peace and stability in the area. Its main goals are to maintain territorial integrity and sovereignty, advance peace and stability, accelerate socioeconomic integration, and strengthen unity and solidarity among African nations. The Peace and Security Council, the African Standby Force, and the Panel of the Wise are components of the African Union's (AU) African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), which is intended to handle disputes. In addition, the AU works to resolve conflicts, maintain peace, aid in reconstruction after a conflict, combat terrorism, and advance democratic governance. It also arranges humanitarian aid and health crisis responses and promotes economic integration through programs like the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

STRENGTHENING GLOBAL SECURITY AND ECONOMIC ALLIANCES

The United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement (USMCA) and the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP) are pivotal frameworks promoting economic integration and global trade. Toro-Fernandez and Tijmes-Ihl (2021, p. 147 and 169) highlight that the USMCA, launched on July 1, 2020, updates NAFTA to enhance trade among the United States, Mexico, and Canada through market access and compliance mechanisms, intellectual property rights, and environmental and labor standards. Similarly, the CPTPP, signed on March 8, 2018, unites eleven Asia-Pacific nations to address market access, investment, and regulatory harmonization. Both agreements emphasize non-tariff trade barriers, regulatory convergence, digital commerce, and environmental norms, which are expected to influence international trade laws and standards, fostering commerce, investment, and economic growth.

China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) aims to enhance global connectivity by investing in transportation, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure, thereby strengthening trade and investment ties with partner countries. This initiative has catalyzed Chinese investments in manufacturing, energy, and real estate, leading to economic growth and job creation. However, concerns about security, debt sustainability, and geopolitical implications have emerged, particularly affecting strategic alignments among Quad countries. Khanal and Chang (2023, pp. 362 and 387) highlight that while Chinese scholars emphasize the BRI's developmental advantages, researchers within the Quad focus on its geopolitical challenges, resulting in policy restrictions on BRI projects and the exploration of alternative infrastructure initiatives.

These evolving trade frameworks and infrastructure initiatives are influenced by technological advancement, scientific progress, and heightened volatility in the post-Cold War era. The proliferation of nuclear weapons, as President Clinton emphasized, remains a paramount global security risk, complicating diplomatic efforts as nations address threats of nuclear terrorism and inadvertent escalation. Nuckolls (1995) illustrates this enduring challenge, noting Senator Sam Nunn's prediction that managing the risk of weapons of mass destruction (WMDs) would be a "top continuous national security challenge for the next ten to twenty years." The risks associated with nuclear proliferation among nations highlight the dual dangers of intentional and accidental nuclear engagement, posing a unique threat to international stability.

Colombo and Lecha (2024, p. 8 and 21) explore how regionalism and diplomacy are affected by the geopolitical dynamics in regions like the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), where Gulf states' influence and the involvement of Russia and China increasingly challenge US dominance. Regional rivalries, notably between Saudi Arabia and Iran, coupled with internal conflicts in countries like Yemen and Syria, fuel instability and limit diplomatic efforts. Europe, particularly the EU, faces mounting challenges, such as increased refugee flows and extremist threats, that demand stronger crisis management capabilities. To navigate these complex dynamics, the EU must reassess its diplomatic strategies and reinforce its conflict-resolution mechanisms to better address emerging regional and global issues.

These challenges underscore the importance of non-traditional security threats beyond conventional military concerns. Peter Hough argues that while military threats remain prevalent, they are no longer the sole threat to global security; issues such as migration, cross-border crime, and cultural conflicts are equally pressing. Juma (2020) supports this view, advocating for solutions that are comprehensive and community-oriented. Successfully addressing these complex issues requires adaptive and inclusive approaches to both regionalism and diplomacy.

Indeed, internal conflicts, economic disparities, and governance issues add further complexity to regional stability and cooperation. Effective diplomacy is hindered by fragmented policies and a lack of coordination among stakeholders, while humanitarian and migration crises place additional strain on regional alliances. Addressing these challenges calls for a multifaceted approach that includes adaptable policies, flexible frameworks, and heightened cooperation between regional and global actors. Boukhars (2019) points out that the success of regional powers often depends on their capacity to manage internal problems, as nations aspiring to regional leadership must address internal instabilities, weak political institutions, and structural issues that impede their ability to take on leadership roles effectively.

Baral (2024, pp. 170 and 181) suggests several strategies to bolster regionalism and address complex security, cultural, and socio-economic issues, recommending a blend of constructivism, neorealism, and neoliberalism to understand regional dynamics. He advocates for public-private partnerships and participation in global forums to foster cooperation, enhance inclusivity by empowering smaller states, and establish policies that promote financial stability. Additionally, Baral emphasizes the importance of updating policy frameworks to address contemporary challenges, as well as strengthening regional organizations to manage new and emerging concerns.

Economic imbalances within regional blocs, as seen in ASEAN, affect collaborative efforts, with more developed economies often reaping greater benefits from initiatives like the BRI than less developed ones. Khanal and Chang (2023, p. 363 and 377) note that disparities in infrastructure and income can exacerbate social tensions and impede integration into global trade. The BRI attempts to mitigate these issues by investing in connectivity and inclusive growth; however, these economic differences present geopolitical challenges that impact cooperative efforts. Achieving sustainable development and equitable investment is essential to reduce inequality and reinforce regional cooperation.

As the global nuclear landscape becomes increasingly complex, with emerging powers such as China, India, and Pakistan developing their arsenals, Miller (2020) highlights that this shift from a binary US-Russia dynamic introduces new risks of escalation. The proliferation of nuclear capabilities in multiple nations amplifies competition and heightens the potential for regional and global tensions, diverting resources from developmental goals toward military expenditures.

Colombo and Lecha (2024, pp. 7–22) conclude that economic and social inequalities within MENA are significant barriers to regional stability. Discrepancies in wealth among Gulf states, alongside rivalry within blocs like the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) and between nations such as Morocco and Algeria, hinder regional cohesion. Policies that promote income redistribution, foster international trust, and support balanced development are necessary to address these inequalities. The EU's role in supporting regional stability through development initiatives and institution-building could help counterbalance internal divisions and foster more inclusive growth.

Finally, economic inequalities within and between regional blocs such as the EU, ASEAN, and the African Union (AU) continue to affect regional cooperation. Toro-Fernandez and Tijmes-Ihl (2021, p. 147) observe that wealth and resource disparities, compounded by security challenges such as nuclear proliferation and regional conflicts, hinder integration efforts. Addressing these issues calls for comprehensive economic initiatives, ethical trade policies, and diplomatic strategies that mitigate security risks while fostering cooperation and stability across regions.

CASE STUDIES:

- Europe: Brexit and the rise of nationalism present problems for the European Union.
- Asia: How China's ascent has affected regional politics and how other neighbors have responded.
- Middle East: The Gulf Cooperation Council and other regional organizations' roles, as well as the current hostilities.
- Africa: Despite internal strife, the African Union works to advance prosperity and peace.
- Americas: Advancing Unity: Progress and Challenges in Mercosur Regional Cooperation and Integration.
- BRICS emergence as a new challenge for NATO

1. Brexit:

Etiubon and Ibietan (2018, p. 34 and 36) highlight Brexit and nationalism as significant challenges to the European Union, leading to strained power dynamics and prompting the EU to reconsider its liberal policies. Brexit not only altered the European Council's balance but also introduced disruptions to the EU's cohesiveness, particularly in trade, financial, and regulatory areas. This shift places additional stress on the EU, as nationalist forces in countries like France and the Netherlands gain influence, further threatening the Union's unity. Likewise, Schmidt (2017) notes that these strains are compounded by security threats, the refugee crisis, and heightened tensions with Russia, which collectively underscore the EU's struggle to maintain a cooperative strategy. The convergence of these issues raises concerns about the EU's democratic legitimacy and institutional resilience, sparking uncertainty over its future. Together, Brexit and rising nationalism question the EU's capability to remain a cohesive force in European and global politics.

The 2016 Brexit referendum marked a defining moment for the European Union (EU), as 51.9% of UK voters chose to leave the bloc, reshaping EU dynamics and intensifying discussions on national sovereignty. Brexit not only impacted the UK but also reverberated across Europe, posing a challenge to the EU's foundation of unity and prompting a rise in nationalist sentiments among member states. This resurgence of nationalism, spurred by skepticism toward EU integration, raises concerns about the future of the EU and its core values of cooperation and inclusivity.

Nationalism in Europe is not a new phenomenon, as various forms of nationalist movements have periodically emerged throughout the 20th century, often responding to crises and fears of cultural erosion. Before Brexit, countries like France and Hungary already experienced a growing nationalist tide, spurred by economic crises and immigration debates. Brexit has acted as a catalyst for these sentiments, emboldening nationalist parties across Europe. Parties advocating sovereignty and skeptical of EU integration gained momentum, viewing Brexit as a success in reclaiming national control. This wave has sparked debates on EU legitimacy and unity, especially in countries where anti-EU sentiment resonates deeply.

The consequences of Brexit and the rise of nationalism reach into the economic, political, and social fabrics of the EU. Economically, the UK's departure disrupts trade and market stability while the rise in economic nationalism across member states challenges the EU's principles of free trade. Politically, Brexit has amplified internal divisions within the EU, with nationalist movements threatening traditional political structures and prompting calls for reform to address citizens' concerns. Socially, nationalism has led to increased polarization, with rhetoric often targeting immigrants and minorities, challenging the EU's foundational principles of inclusivity and solidarity. The EU's future now depends on its ability to address these growing divides and adapt to an evolving political landscape that prioritizes both unity and respect for member states' sovereignty.

Figure 1: NATO, EU, Schengen and Eurozone member states in Europe

Source: https://www.reddit.com/r/MapPorn/comments/1bg22oy/nato_eu_schengen_and_eurozone_member_states_in/#lightbox

2. ASEAN:

China's rapid ascent has significantly altered Asia's geopolitical landscape, challenging the region's established dynamics and prompting diverse responses from neighboring countries. According to Pelaudeix (2023), ASEAN nations have strategically adopted hedging techniques to balance engagement with China while diversifying alliances. Institutions like the East Asia Summit and the ASEAN Regional Forum foster open discourse aimed at offsetting China's influence. However, ASEAN's internal diversity and susceptibility to external pressures complicate its efforts to maintain centrality and independence, while China's economic clout influences regional autonomy through frameworks like Mercosur and ASEAN.

China's assertiveness, highlighted by its military expansion and the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), has significantly altered the balance of power in Asia, particularly in its relations with countries like Vietnam, the Philippines, and Japan. This shift has prompted a broader arms race and heightened security concerns, leading nations to adapt their foreign policies. In response, the U.S. has rebalanced its focus towards the Asia-Pacific, while Japan is revising its defense strategies, and South Korea seeks a diplomatic approach that balances relations with both China and the U.S. Concurrently, the EU is enhancing its strategic cooperation with ASEAN to reinforce a rules-based order and uphold democratic values in the region.

The BRI, launched in 2013, is pivotal to China's foreign policy, aiming to enhance regional connectivity through significant infrastructure investments, such as railways and ports. While the in-

initiative brings potential economic advantages for participating nations, it also raises concerns about debt dependency and an increased Chinese influence over smaller countries. However, China's ascendancy is not without its challenges. Territorial disputes in the South China Sea have intensified tensions with neighboring states and the U.S., while ongoing trade conflicts with the U.S. and Europe over trade practices add to these complications. As China navigates these domestic and international challenges, including an aging population and economic inequality, its ability to maintain influence within Asia's evolving geopolitical landscape remains uncertain.

Figure 2: Maps of ASEAN Countries with their National Flags and Costumes Posters

Source: <https://www.ost.co.th/en/product/1914/posters-ep-492>

3. Gulf Cooperation Council

Del Sarto and Lecha (2024, p. 1447 and 1467) explain that six Gulf countries make up the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), which was founded in 1981 and initially focused on economic cooperation. However, the GCC also had a significant impact on regional security. Despite some early successes, the GCC has been deeply divided, as revealed in 2017 when Qatar was boycotted by Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Bahrain, and Egypt due to accusations of supporting terrorism and interfering in domestic affairs. Other regional organizations, such as the Arab League, which has struggled with internal strife and poor collaboration, face similar challenges. Effective regional cooperation is hampered by current hostilities, including the ongoing GCC crisis, the civil war in Syria, the conflict in Yemen, and differing opinions on the normalization of relations with Israel. These issues highlight the necessity for the GCC to address internal divisions to enhance its effectiveness in regional security.

Research on financial contagion has received a lot of attention, particularly since the 2008 Global Financial Crisis (GFC). According to early research by Engle et al. (1990), trade and financial ties are the means by which financial volatility is propagated. These theories are known as the "heat-wave" and "meteor shower" theories. Studies conducted in the MENA area show that there is little market integration among MENA stock markets, although there are significant links with developed markets. Financial Stress Indexes (FSI) have gained popularity as a tool for evaluating

financial spillovers; they demonstrate that the GFC exacerbated spillovers and that MENA markets react slowly to outside information. Financial strain and oil prices have a complicated relationship; both before and after the Great Financial Crisis, there is evidence of bidirectional volatility spillovers. This underscores the necessity of additional research on the interplay between oil price and financial stress in the region, given their noteworthy influence on the GCC nations. Understanding these financial dynamics is crucial for GCC member states as they navigate economic challenges amid regional political tensions.

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) enhances regional security through its defense planning council and the Peninsula Shield Force, which are vital given the geopolitical tensions in the Middle East, especially concerning Iran. Joint military exercises and intelligence-sharing agreements strengthen the collective defense capabilities of member states. Politically, the GCC fosters dialogue and coordination, allowing for a unified stance during crises, as evidenced during the Arab Spring. Additionally, the Council promotes cultural ties and social exchanges among its members through initiatives in education and tourism, fostering a shared identity. Furthermore, substantial investments in infrastructure projects in transportation and energy sectors enhance connectivity and economic growth, benefiting all member states and contributing to regional development. These initiatives not only address security concerns but also aim to mitigate the economic vulnerabilities highlighted in the research on financial contagion, ultimately supporting the GCC's stability and resilience in a complex geopolitical landscape.

Figure 3: Gulf Cooperation Council Countries

Source:

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Map-of-the-Gulf-Cooperation-Council-Countries-Saudi-Arabia-UAE-United-Arab-Emirates_fig1_268880140

4. The Arab Maghreb Union

The Arab Maghreb Union (UMA), established in 1989, aims to promote economic integration and regional stability among Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and Mauritania by facilitating trade and coordinated policies, as noted by Colombo and Lecha (2024, pp. 8, 21). However, its effectiveness is undermined by internal rivalries, particularly between Algeria and Morocco, along with security issues such as political instability and Islamic extremism. This challenge is echoed in other regional organizations like the Arab League (LEA) and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), which similarly struggle with internal conflicts and ideological divisions that hinder their progress toward cooperation and development.

Political tensions, particularly the dispute over Western Sahara, have further impeded UMA's ability to establish a common market and unified foreign policy, despite some early successes in sectors like agriculture and transportation, according to DIFADI (2024, p. 226 and 230). Internal rivalries, along with issues like industrial inefficiency, climate dependency, rapid population growth, and high unemployment, have contributed to the UMA's stagnation. Addressing these challenges, such as harmonizing accounting laws, is critical for revitalizing regional integration and reevaluating the UMA's objectives and approaches.

The security landscape in North Africa has become increasingly complex, driven by the rise of extremist groups and the spillover effects of conflicts in neighboring regions like the Sahel. In response, the UMA has attempted to enhance cooperation through initiatives focused on border security, intelligence sharing, and joint military operations. However, the organization faces criticism for its limited operational capacity and political cohesion, with divergent national interests often hindering collective action. This perception of the UMA as an "invisible" entity in regional security highlights the need for a robust institutional framework and a unified approach among member states. To fulfill its potential in enhancing regional security, the UMA must address these operational challenges and foster greater integration among its members, contributing to overall stability in North Africa.

Figure 4: The Arab Maghreb Union

Source: <https://studies.aljazeera.net/en/reports/2015/01/201512713642692743.html>

5. The African Union

The African Union (AU), established on July 26, 2002, in Durban, South Africa, is a continental union comprising 55 member states and succeeded the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), which was founded in 1963. The AU marks a significant shift from focusing on liberation struggles to promoting economic development, political stability, and integration among African nations. Its primary objectives include fostering unity, defending sovereignty, and enhancing socio-economic integration across various sectors such as political governance, human rights, and security, while advocating for democratic principles and good governance. Key institutions include the African Union Commission (AUC) and the Pan-African Parliament. The AU's landmark initiative, the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), aims to create a single market for goods and services, enhancing intra-African trade and economic growth. The AU's vision is outlined in Agenda 2063, which focuses on inclusive and sustainable development, peace, and security, striving to transform Africa into a global powerhouse.

However, the AU faces numerous obstacles, including internal conflict, economic inequality, and security risks, as noted by Gelot and Söderbaum (2023, p. 822 and 834). Despite these challenges, the AU employs a comprehensive strategy to promote peace and prosperity across the continent. A key initiative is the African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), which includes the African Standby Force (ASF), the Panel of the Wise, and the Peace and Security Council (PSC) for monitoring and resolving disputes. Furthermore, through the AfCFTA, the AU fosters economic integration, mediates disputes, and aids in post-conflict rehabilitation. The organization also manages health emergencies, supports capacity building, advocates for human rights and democratic governance, coordinates humanitarian assistance, and collaborates with foreign groups. Although financial limitations and political barriers within member nations pose challenges, the AU remains essential to advancing peace and development in Africa.

H.E. Moussa Faki Mahamat, Chairperson of the African Union Commission, emphasized the need for a comprehensive approach to Africa's security issues, citing conflicts and humanitarian crises in Sudan, Somalia, and the Sahel. H.E. Dhoahir Dhoulkamal highlighted terrorism and political instability as significant threats to democracy, noting stalled political transitions in Mali, Niger, and Burkina Faso. Meanwhile, H.E. Taye Atske-Selassie praised the African Union's efforts in resolving the Ethiopian conflict and stressed the importance of effectively implementing Agenda 2063. H.E. Claver Gatete called for improved education systems to align with job market needs and leverage technological advancements. Additionally, the AU's G20 membership presents a key opportunity for global influence, with upcoming discussions focusing on trade, integration, and education, as noted in an African Union Press Release (2024).

Figure 5: The African Union

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Regions-of-the-African-Union-according-to-the-African-Union-classification_fig1_363811653

6. Mercosur

Mercosur, or the Southern Common Market, is a regional trade bloc established in 1991, originally comprising Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay, with Bolivia joining as a full member in 2023. Its primary aim is to promote economic integration, trade, and investment among member states while enhancing political dialogue and stability in the region, largely as a response to historical rivalries, particularly between Argentina and Brazil. Over the years, Mercosur has evolved into one of the world's largest economic blocs, with a combined GDP exceeding \$2.6 trillion as of 2022, significantly boosting intra-regional trade from \$4 billion in 1990 to over \$41 billion by 2010. Despite these successes, the bloc faces challenges such as internal divisions, economic inequality, and geopolitical pressures, which may affect its future viability. Security governance within Mercosur is rooted in democracy and human rights, with mechanisms for political dialogue and conflict resolution. Internal security concerns, such as organized crime and drug trafficking, alongside external challenges from major global powers, highlight the need for member states to collaborate on security measures. The interplay between security and economic development is critical, as a secure environment fosters investor confidence and trade, while insecurity can hinder economic growth and budget allocations for development programs.

From early 2022 to mid-2023, Pena et al. (2023) examine the achievements and obstacles of Mercosur's regional integration and collaboration. The member states—Uruguay, Brazil, Paraguay, and Argentina—despite their strategic differences, have made significant progress within the bloc. Notable achievements include advancements in the Common External Tariff (CET), a recovery in commerce and foreign direct investment post-pandemic, and institutional developments like the Structural Convergence Fund (FOCEM), as well as new agendas addressing digital and environmental issues. Additionally, biotechnology initiatives have progressed alongside ex-

tensive discussions with other countries on external relations. Nonetheless, persistent challenges remain, including internal disputes, unresolved issues regarding economic integration, and difficulties in signing trade agreements with external nations. Overall, Mercosur continues to strive for greater integration despite these ongoing obstacles.

Galeano (2024, p. 61-63) highlights that Paraguay's budget increased by 299,069,772,479 guaraníes in 2023, reaching 2,969,119,995,928 guaraníes, up from 2,670,050,223,449 guaraníes in 2022. However, customs revenue, essential for funding healthcare and education, was adversely affected by the CMC 08/2022 standard's reduction in import tariffs. While customs collections initially rose, the tariff cuts led to revenue fluctuations, with some months experiencing increases while others saw declines. Overall, the reduction in tariffs contributed to decreased customs revenue, although import volume and commodity value also influenced these trends. The significant impact on public health expenditures and services necessitates further long-term analysis and comparative studies among Mercosur nations to fully assess the broader effects.

Figure 6: Mercosur

Source: <https://geopoliticalfutures.com/mercosurs-changing-trade-patterns/>

Usman et al. (2023, pp. 56 and 67) examine the economic and environmental challenges facing Mercosur countries, with an emphasis on energy consumption, natural resource management, technological advancements, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The report emphasizes the struggle to balance environmental sustainability with economic growth, as resource exploitation has increased GHG emissions and hindered climate action. While renewable energy adoption and technological advancements are crucial for reducing pollution, overuse of natural resources remains a concern. The authors advocate for investments in human capital, enhanced environmental regulations, and decreased reliance on non-renewable resources. Despite these challenges, Mercosur countries are committed to sustainable development, aligning their policies with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

7. BRICS

The emergence of BRICS as a coalition of major emerging economies presents a significant challenge for NATO, especially with Turkey's interest in joining the bloc. As BRICS expands its influence, it aims to create an alternative to Western dominance in global governance, which could undermine NATO's strategic cohesion and lead to potential divisions among its members. The collective economic and demographic power of BRICS may shift global dynamics, prompting NATO to reassess its strategies and alliances in a multipolar world. This evolving landscape requires NATO to adopt a nuanced approach to maintain its relevance and effectiveness in an increasingly complex international environment. As this transformation unfolds, the implications for NATO's operational and strategic frameworks could be profound, necessitating a recalibration of priorities.

As a significant player in global affairs, BRICS—comprising Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—addresses pressing issues such as climate change and sustainable development, often contrasting with NATO's traditional focus on military readiness and collective defense. BRICS positions itself as a voice for developing nations, advocating for a multilateral approach to global challenges that emphasizes equity and inclusivity. This divergence in priorities can create tensions between the two coalitions, as BRICS critiques Western-centric policies promoted by NATO, which may prioritize immediate security concerns over long-term sustainability. This ongoing friction highlights the need for NATO to not only recognize BRICS' growing influence but also to engage with these emerging economies in a manner that aligns with their priorities, fostering dialogue rather than discord.

The formation of the BRICS alliance has emerged as a significant challenge for NATO in the current global geopolitical landscape. As a collective of leading emerging economies, BRICS is actively shaping the international order in ways that often diverge from the traditional Western-led framework promoted by NATO (Ruppel & Ruppel-Schlichting, 2013). A key challenge posed by BRICS to NATO lies in its advocacy for a multipolar world order. The BRICS nations consistently push for a more inclusive and equitable global governance system, emphasizing a more balanced distribution of power among various regional and economic blocs. This stands in stark contrast to NATO's historical role as a transatlantic security alliance, which has primarily focused on maintaining Western hegemony in the post-Cold War era. The differing priorities and approaches of BRICS and NATO highlight the complexities of contemporary international relations and the shifting dynamics of global power, urging NATO to rethink its strategies to engage with these emerging powers constructively.

Furthermore, BRICS has been proactive in establishing alternative financial and economic institutions, including the New Development Bank and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement, which serve as counterweights to the Western-dominated International Monetary Fund and World Bank (Denisov et al., 2019). This shift in the global economic architecture challenges NATO's influence and the centrality of the West in international affairs, as it offers developing nations more options for financial support and investment, reducing reliance on traditional Western institutions. This emerging economic framework not only empowers BRICS nations but also un-

derscores the potential for a redefined global economic order, one that could further complicate NATO's strategic landscape.

Additionally, the BRICS alliance has adopted a distinct approach to global issues, such as climate change and sustainable development, which often contrasts with NATO's traditional policy priorities. While NATO primarily focuses on military readiness and geopolitical stability, BRICS emphasizes the importance of addressing socio-economic factors that contribute to global instability, including environmental sustainability. This divergence in priorities can lead to tensions between the two blocs, particularly in international forums where differing strategies may clash over resource allocation and responses to global challenges. The increasing prominence of BRICS in shaping international discussions reflects a broader demand for a more equitable and representative global governance framework, urging NATO to adapt and engage more constructively with these emerging coalitions to address shared global challenges effectively.

Figure 7: BRICS

Source: <https://www.metropoles.com/brasil/brasil-assume-presidencia-dos-brics-em-2025-veja-o-que-esperar>

WORLD WAR III OR A COLD WAR REDUX: EVALUATING GLOBAL RISKS

According to Carafano et al. (2023, p. 16–20), there are some striking similarities and differences between the current tensions with China and the initial Cold War. The United States and the Soviet Union were the main enemies during the first Cold War, with the Soviet Union being a military rival but not an economic one. On the other hand, the U.S. and China are currently engaged in a rivalry where China has emerged as a significant economic powerhouse and a military one that is modernizing quickly. Even though both wars are fought on a worldwide scale, the contemporary Cold War is distinguished by its emphasis on economic coercion and influence rather than direct military conflict and its economic interconnectedness. The competition in technology has also changed, including fields like cybersecurity and artificial intelligence. Even while the ideological gap between democracy and authoritarianism still exists, there are new obstacles brought about by the advanced technical landscape and the interconnected global economy that

call for a nuanced strategy to keep things stable and prevent confrontation. This understanding of the complexities surrounding U.S.-China relations helps contextualize the broader implications for global stability.

Alperovitch (2024) claims that Xi Jinping and President Joe Biden openly oppose the idea of a new Cold War between the United States and China, prioritizing collaboration above hostilities. Still, there are many parallels between the contemporary geopolitical environment and the original Cold War, as both superpowers compete for supremacy in the military, economic, and technical spheres worldwide. With some major exceptions, like a strong degree of economic interdependence, the dynamics of Cold War I are echoed in this new era of armaments races, increased espionage, and space competition. Rather than existential dangers, the strategic contest between the United States and China is centered on worldwide influence. To handle this intricate struggle and avert possible war, the United States must strengthen its advantages and strategic allies. Thus, while leaders may publicly downplay the rivalry, the underlying tensions remain potent and influential in shaping policies and alliances.

Technology and cyberwarfare are crucial in the context of a possible Cold War II with China, as noted by Carafano et al. (2023, p. 17 and 53). One of the main issues is the rampant theft of intellectual property in China, which hinders innovation and favors the Communist Party militarily and economically. By using cyberwarfare to threaten American national infrastructure, China aspires to become the dominant force in cutting-edge fields like artificial intelligence and quantum computing. Furthermore, the military uses of China's biotechnology advancements may have an effect on international security. Geopolitical objectives are achieved through economic pressure and influence, making it necessary for the United States to safeguard its economy and diversify its technological base. In order to counter these threats and fortify the global technology infrastructure, collaboration with allies is essential. This highlights the importance of technology not only as a tool for competition but also as a potential flashpoint for conflict, necessitating strategic cooperation among allies to navigate these complex challenges.

According to Evers (2024), as part of a larger strategy to contain Chinese dominance, the United States has put restrictions on China's access to sophisticated semiconductors. Experts contend that the plan is unlikely to succeed in spite of these efforts. American companies oppose export prohibitions, and China is quickly developing its own semiconductor sector with significant government funding and subsidies. American companies dominate high-value design in the global semiconductor value chain, while Chinese companies handle lower-value assembly. Difficulties facing the U.S. plan include business pushback and slower domestic manufacturing, as well as the Science Act and CHIPS. The Biden administration may need to reevaluate its strategy in order to succeed, striking a balance between the needs of global business and home industry support. The challenges posed by economic interdependence illustrate the intricacies of navigating U.S.-China relations, where economic strategies must be carefully calibrated to avoid unintended consequences that could further entrench competition.

The competition between the United States and China, also called the "New Cold War," is characterized by fierce economic and ideological conflict, as noted by Carafano et al. (2023, p. 20 and

23). The United States and China have a close economic relationship, which makes isolation tactics more difficult, and China's trade policies give rise to worries about unfair trade practices and intellectual property theft. Both countries are engaged in a strong competition to preserve technological supremacy in developing fields like artificial intelligence (AI) and quantum computing. From an ideological perspective, they stand for diametrically opposed systems—autarky vs democracy—and compete for control over international norms and governance. China strategically attacks U.S. interests through intellectual exchanges and economic pressure, therefore the country needs a strong plan to protect its competitive advantage and standing in the world. This ideological struggle further complicates the geopolitical landscape, as both nations seek to leverage their respective strengths in technology and trade to secure influence over global governance structures.

Hughes (2024, pp. 20–22) claims that the tiny transnational ruling class staged a global technocratic coup in 2020 in an effort to maintain its supremacy in the face of a breakdown of class compromise, amid a serious global class war fueled by a failing oligarchic capitalism. There have been suggestions that this "pseudopandemic" is a pretext for a worldwide coup d'état, and some members of the ruling class are using the parallels to World War II to defend drastic structural reforms. The pandemic's effects, which are seen in previously unheard-of excess mortality rates in a number of nations, imply that the current situation has similarities to the catastrophic tendencies of earlier global conflicts. The extra deaths, which are mostly attributable to government actions, highlight how serious the current global struggle is. It involves significant societal disruption and suffering, much like earlier world conflicts. This perspective of societal upheaval complements the narrative of geopolitical tension, as the global response to crises shapes not only national strategies but also international alliances and rivalries.

The World War III scenario is represented in the graph below, which shows the alliances and relationships between the transnational ruling elite, as well as their goal of establishing technocratic control over the majority of people on Earth. This depiction emphasizes the interconnectedness of global power dynamics, illustrating how the tensions between the U.S. and China are not only a matter of bilateral relations but are influenced by broader structural issues that reflect a deepening global crisis. The complexities of these relationships require careful navigation and strategic foresight to avoid escalating conflicts into larger global confrontations. In light of these factors, it becomes evident that understanding the multifaceted interactions between technology, economics, and political ideologies is crucial for formulating effective responses to the challenges posed by the current international landscape.

Graph 1: WWII scenario

Source: Developed by the author

According to Hughes (2024, p. 23–24), in the case of a third world war, the transnational ruling class, distinguished by its extraordinary wealth and its hold over vital societal sectors, covertly targets the global majority in order to construct a worldwide technocracy that is supervised by cutting-edge technology and surveillance. The Global Power Elite from America and Europe, comprising the richest 10% of the population, businesses, and international institutions like the WHO, IMF, and WEF, are important participants in this scheme. This small but powerful group aims to maintain control over humanity, and should their true objectives be discovered, they risk igniting a worldwide revolution. They utilize deceit and misinformation to stay in power, reflecting a broader struggle for influence that transcends national borders and highlights the interconnectedness of political and economic systems.

As Scott (2024) reports, former United States Chief of Staff General Sir Patrick Sanders cautions NATO members that we are living in the most hazardous time since 1945 and calls for more investment in weapons. He names Iran, China, and Russia as the "new axis powers," suggesting they could be even more dangerous than the Nazis in 1939. If nothing is done, he believes a third world war could break out in five years. To avert war, Sanders emphasizes that NATO must update its armed capabilities and close any capacity deficiencies. His warnings resonate with

Hughes's concerns about the elite's manipulation of global crises, suggesting that the military strategies pursued by nations are intertwined with the larger narratives constructed by the ruling class to maintain power.

Hughes (2024) acknowledges that the World War III scenario recognizes socio-political and economic factors reflecting transnational class strife as catalysts for global conflict. These factors include the inability of the "War on Terror" to control social movements, indications of a 2019 financial system collapse, a crisis in mainstream media credibility, and the "Covid-19" operation, which served as a cover for biosecurity and psychological warfare. Historical analogies are drawn between the use of global wars to enact drastic reforms and the transition to technocratic rule. This analysis underscores that contemporary conflicts are not merely military in nature but are deeply rooted in societal structures and inequalities, challenging the notion that traditional warfare is the only path to conflict resolution.

Kampeas (2024) writes that after a three-year hiatus, former President Donald Trump and Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu reconciled amicably. During their meeting at Mar-a-Lago, Trump criticized the Biden administration, claiming it has pushed the world toward potential major conflicts, including a Third World War. Trump highlighted his past support for Israel, citing achievements such as the Abraham Accords and the recognition of Jerusalem as Israel's capital. The meeting was cordial, with Trump and Netanyahu expressing mutual support despite previous disagreements. If re-elected, Trump promised to bring peace to the Middle East. This engagement illustrates how international relations are influenced by individual leaders' decisions, reflecting a potential shift in alliances and strategies that could either exacerbate or mitigate the risks of broader conflict.

Rakgomo (2024) states that headlines express concern over the rising tensions between Israel and Iran, raising the possibility of a third world war. However, World War III is not a distant threat but a reality manifesting as irregular, low-intensity battles. Today's warfare includes drone strikes, covert operations, and proxy wars, undermining international peace and security. This shift is evident in the Israeli-Palestinian and Syrian conflicts, where resolutions are complicated by regional and international powers. Similarly, the "war on terror" involves covert alliances that foster instability. This widespread conflict is also visible in South Asia, Yemen, Ukraine, the South China Sea, and the Korean peninsula. As countries like Switzerland and Sweden become involved in global disputes, traditional neutrality is eroding. The evolving nature of warfare and conflict dynamics highlighted by Rakgomo reinforces the urgency for diplomatic efforts to resolve tensions, emphasizing that proactive engagement rather than reactive military responses may be critical to avoiding a larger conflict.

According to VOA News (2024), in the wake of recent Chinese naval drills nearby, Taiwan's defense ministry discovered a record 66 Chinese military aircraft circling the island in a 24-hour period. Tensions over Taiwan's sovereignty are at an all-time high, and this spike in Chinese military action includes 56 planes crossing the median line across the Taiwan Strait. Beijing has promised to use force if necessary and regards Taiwan as part of its territory. The augmentation of military presence aligns with recent political happenings, such as a meeting between Taiwanese Presi-

dent Lai Ching-te and Washington's new de facto ambassador to Taiwan. The Chinese aircraft activity is indicative of ongoing regional tensions, especially disputes in the South China Sea, and comes after a similar high in May. This situation exemplifies the precarious balance of power in the region, highlighting the need for strategic diplomacy and the potential for military escalation, echoing the concerns raised by Hughes and Scott regarding the role of elite interests in shaping the geopolitical landscape.

THE ROLE OF DIPLOMACY, PREVENTIVE DIPLOMACY, AND TRACK II DIPLOMACY

Diplomacy and preventive diplomacy are essential for maintaining international peace and security. Key organizations such as the United Nations, NATO, and BRICS significantly contribute to these efforts. The United Nations Charter emphasizes the organization's main goal of preserving peace through collective, peaceful, and preventive measures, including taking effective actions to prevent threats and address acts of aggression (Mani, 2009). This foundational principle underlines the necessity for global collaboration to mitigate conflicts before they escalate, thereby fostering a stable international environment.

Using philosophy and religion to promote peace, Tobisawa (2024, p. 4 and 30) outlines a number of strategies for preventing and resolving conflicts. These include proactive preventive diplomacy, which addresses tensions before they escalate, cultural and educational exchanges, direct dialogues with political and social leaders, advocacy for nuclear disarmament, specific peace proposals and political initiatives like the "Hiroshima Action Plan," and international support through multilateral cooperation with organizations like UNESCO. These strategies demonstrate the multifaceted approach required for effective diplomacy, which combines political, cultural, and educational efforts to build trust and reduce tensions between states. The aim is to establish world security and peace, reflecting the interconnected nature of diplomatic efforts.

Between conflict prevention and peacekeeping lies the task of resolving disputes through peaceful means, as detailed in Chapter VI of the UN Charter and expanded in declarations like the Manila Declaration of 1982 and the 1988 Declaration on Threats to International Peace and Security. Effective international peace and security maintenance is crucial not just to prevent armed conflicts, but also to address related issues such as reversing the global arms race, alleviating poverty, protecting human rights, and safeguarding the environment (Boutros - Ghali, 1992). This comprehensive perspective on security highlights that diplomacy must address a wide range of interlinked global challenges, emphasizing the necessity of a holistic approach to peacebuilding.

Tobisawa (2024, pp. 7 and 28) believes that international institutions such as the United Nations (UN) are essential in the prevention and resolution of conflicts within the framework of preventive diplomacy. The UN organizes conferences like the NPT Review Conference, provides a neutral forum for discussion and negotiation, and monitors and reports on potential disputes. It manages public education programs, promotes transparency and confidence-building measures,

and oversees the implementation of international treaties and disarmament agreements. This role of the UN is pivotal in fostering a culture of cooperation and dialogue, enabling nations to work together in addressing the root causes of conflict rather than merely responding to its symptoms.

Successful diplomatic efforts include the Camp David Accords (1978), where U.S. mediation resulted in the first peace treaty between an Arab nation and Israel; the Good Friday Agreement (1998), which established a government with shared authority and ended much of the violence in Northern Ireland; and the Iran Nuclear Deal (2015), a significant agreement between Iran and the P5+1 to prevent Iran from obtaining nuclear weapons, according to Shannoun (2023, p. 215 and 225). On the other hand, instances of unsuccessful diplomatic attempts include the Rwandan Genocide (1994), where global efforts were unable to stop the mass murder of people; the ongoing Syrian Civil War (2011-present), despite multiple peace negotiations; and the Venezuela Crisis (2010s), in which diplomatic attempts failed to resolve the political or humanitarian problems. These contrasting examples illustrate the complexities of diplomacy, highlighting that successful outcomes often depend on timing, the willingness of parties to engage, and the ability to navigate entrenched interests.

Adam (2023, pp. 509–513) discusses how Machiavelli argued that in anarchic societies, governments must balance the use of force and diplomacy to survive and thrive, as demonstrated by his political realism theory. Machiavelli's ideas reflect the 16th-century political context, emphasizing that states must navigate a world devoid of a supreme moral authority or divine guidance through a mix of force and diplomacy. In contrast, Dr. Jane Knight's book **Knowledge Diplomacy** challenges this pessimistic view by exploring how innovation, research, and higher education can enhance international relations without sacrificing moral principles. Knight proposes that knowledge diplomacy—encompassing scientific collaboration and higher education—provides a framework for positive global interactions based on reciprocity and mutual benefit, as opposed to the power-focused approach of traditional diplomacy. This perspective suggests that integrating moral considerations into diplomacy can foster more sustainable and just international relationships.

Prantl and Goh (2022, p. 446 and 463) emphasize that, given the complexity of the twenty-first century, multilateralism is crucial for resolving issues at the regional level. They draw attention to the way non-state actors are gaining power over states and the emergence of multi-actor networks. It is believed that traditional state-centric diplomacy is less effective in addressing global challenges. Addressing global issues like pandemics, peacebuilding, and power competition in Asia requires a multilateral approach. The authors propose using a Strategic Diplomacy (SD) paradigm that avoids zero-sum strategies and involves a variety of stakeholders. This call for a strategic approach aligns with Tobisawa's advocacy for multilateral cooperation, emphasizing that inclusive dialogues are essential for managing the complexities of contemporary global issues.

Tobisawa (2024, p. 7 and 29) examines case studies of diplomatic initiatives that succeeded and failed. A few successful instances are the Helsinki Accords (1975), which reduced tensions throughout Europe; Daisaku Ikeda's private diplomacy with the USSR; and the Good Friday

Agreement (1998), which restored peace to Northern Ireland. In contrast, the near-nuclear conflict during the Cuban Missile Crisis, the inability of the League of Nations to handle the Manchurian Crisis, and the ongoing Syrian Civil War serve as examples of unsuccessful attempts at diplomacy. This analysis reinforces the notion that while some diplomatic efforts yield positive outcomes, others highlight the limitations and challenges inherent in international negotiations, underscoring the need for adaptive strategies and continuous engagement.

Discussing the expanding importance of NGOs and unofficial channels in contemporary diplomacy, Shannoun (2023, p. 216 and 224) highlights their diverse roles and impact. NGOs contribute through coalition building, public diplomacy, conflict mediation, humanitarian aid delivery, and providing expertise and local knowledge. They also play a role in advocacy, raising awareness on issues like environmental preservation and human rights, and advancing international norms. Their effectiveness varies depending on the context and specific actors, with the International Campaign to Ban Landmines serving as a notable example of success. However, NGOs face challenges such as limited authority, funding constraints, and potential fragmentation. Their success often depends on collaboration with governments and other international entities to leverage their strengths and enhance diplomatic efforts. This highlights the necessity of a collaborative approach that integrates various actors in the diplomatic landscape, recognizing that diverse contributions can enrich efforts toward peace and stability.

The 21st century's changing diplomacy is examined by Prantl and Goh (2022, p. 444 and 460), who draw attention to the transfer of power from states to non-state players and the emergence of multi-actor networks in international collaboration. In this environment, non-governmental actors (NGAs) and unofficial channels play a critical role in fostering diplomacy through their adaptability, diversity of networks, inventiveness, and support of official initiatives. Their interconnectivity, adaptability, and risk management are key components of their efficacy. Despite its benefits, NGAs have limits and are unable to solve global problems on their own. The strengths of formal and informal actors must be integrated within a strategic framework for effective diplomacy. All things considered, NGAs are important, especially when they support official diplomatic initiatives, reinforcing the idea that effective diplomacy in the modern era requires an inclusive, multi-layered approach that leverages the strengths of both state and non-state actors.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to accomplish shared goals like political stability and economic cooperation, regionalism emphasizes the need for fostering political, economic, and cultural linkages between countries within particular regions. The development of regionalism from state-centric alliances in the Cold War to the vibrant, diverse new regionalism of the post-Cold War era has been extensively covered in this article. This transformation reflects a shift in how nations perceive their interconnectedness and the necessity of collaboration in addressing contemporary challenges. The European Union (EU), Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), and Mercosur are important examples of regional organizations that highlight the difficulties and complications these blocs

confront in adjusting to political unrest, economic inequality, and globalization. These organizations not only represent regional cooperation but also illustrate the complexities of navigating diverse political landscapes and economic disparities among member states. Realist and constructivist theoretical frameworks shed light on the ways in which changing identities and power relations affect regional integration and global diplomacy, suggesting that both material interests and ideational factors are crucial in shaping regional dynamics.

Numerous regional blocs and alliances that have an impact on international politics, the economy, and security have shaped the current global environment. The stability of the area and the world is greatly influenced by organizations like the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), BRICS, and NATO. These blocs exemplify the varying objectives and strategies employed by states in pursuit of security and economic interests, illustrating the interplay between regional aspirations and global geopolitical tensions. However, these organizations face enormous difficulties from the escalation of social unrest, economic inequality, and security issues, including nuclear proliferation and regional wars. The strategic rivalry between the United States and China may spark a third World War or a new Cold War, according to the article. This highlights the precarious balance that regional organizations must maintain in a multipolar world, where competing interests often hinder collective action. Such dynamics suggest the necessity for complex diplomatic solutions to resolve these tensions and preserve international peace, indicating that addressing underlying issues requires not only regional cooperation but also a commitment to multilateral dialogue.

Avoiding wars and tackling global issues need proactive and deliberate diplomacy. In this context, international institutions such as the UN and regional entities must step up their diplomatic efforts, emphasizing preventative diplomacy, multilateralism, and the engagement of non-state players. The emphasis on proactive diplomacy indicates a shift from reactive measures to a more anticipatory approach that seeks to address conflicts before they escalate. In a world that is changing quickly, peace and prosperity depend on cooperative and flexible diplomacy. This flexibility is essential for adapting to the evolving challenges posed by globalization, technological advancement, and shifting power dynamics. The future of global cooperation depends on the adaptability and cohesion of regional alliances, the accomplishment of diplomatic endeavors, and the capacity to control threats and disputes. This interconnectedness underscores the need for a holistic approach that integrates various actors, both state and non-state, in the pursuit of sustainable solutions.

Achieving peace and stability necessitates improved international cooperation, stronger diplomatic ties, and a focus on security. This interconnected approach recognizes that regional stability is essential for global security, requiring nations to collaboratively tackle common challenges. Effective collaboration hinges on trust and communication, especially amid uncertainty. The success of regionalism and global diplomacy ultimately depends on states' readiness to engage in meaningful dialogue and work together toward shared objectives, underscoring the importance of diplomacy in navigating international relations.

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